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PYEZOELEKTRIK DATCHIKLARINING ASOSIY PARAMETRLARINI ANIQLASH

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***Annotatsiya:** Bilimlarni o'zlashtirish muammosi kasbiy ta'lim o'qituvchilarini azaldan bezovta qilib kelgan. Hayotda insonning deyarli har qanday harakati, nafaqat o'rganish, balki ma'lum bir bilimlarni, u yoki bu ma'lumotlarni o'zlashtirish va qayta ishlash zarurati bilan bog'liq. O'rganishni o'rgatish, ya'ni ma'lumotni assilyatsiya qilish va to'g'ri ishlashga o'rgatish - bu o'quv faoliyatiga asoslangan yondashuvning asosiy tezisi. Ushbu maqolada pyezoelektrik datchik parametrlarini hisoblashni, o'lchash natijalarini matematik tahlil etish uslubiyotini, pyezoelektrik datchik kirish kattaligi kuch, chiqish kattaligi tok miqdori bo'lgan generator tipidagi datchiklar haqida ma'lumot topish o'rganilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Pyezoelektrik datchik, parametr, kirish kattaligi, chiqish kattaligi, generator, pyezoeffekt hodisasiga, elektr zaryad, kvars, turmalin, segnet tuzi, bariy titanat, membrana.*

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ОСНОВНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ПЬЕЗОЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСКИХ ДАТЧИКОВ

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***Аннотация:** Проблема усвоения знаний давно беспокоит преподавателей профессионального образования. В жизни почти каждое действие человека связано не только с обучением, но и с необходимостью усваивать и обрабатывать определённые знания и информацию. Учить учиться, то есть учить усваивать информацию и правильно её использовать, - это основной тезис подхода, основанного на учебной деятельности. В данной статье рассматриваются методы расчета параметров пьезоэлектрических датчиков,*

методики математического анализа результатов измерений, а также информация о датчиках генераторного типа, у которых входной величиной является сила, а выходной величиной является ток.

Ключевые слова: Пьезоэлектрический датчик, параметр, входная величина, выходная величина, генератор, пьезоэффект, электрический заряд, кварц, турмалин, сегнетова соль, титанат бария, мембрана.

DETERMINATION OF THE MAIN PARAMETERS OF PIEZOELECTRIC SENSORS

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Annotation: The problem of mastering knowledge has long troubled vocational education teachers. In life, almost every human action is related not only to learning but also to the necessity of assimilating and processing certain knowledge and information. Teaching how to learn, that is, teaching how to assimilate information and use it correctly, is the main thesis of the approach based on educational activities. This article discusses methods for calculating the parameters of piezoelectric sensors, methodologies for the mathematical analysis of measurement results, and information about generator-type sensors where the input quantity is force and the output quantity is current.

Keywords: Piezoelectric sensor, parameter, input quantity, output quantity, generator, piezoelectric effect, electric charge, quartz, tourmaline, Rochelle salt, barium titanate, membrane.

Pyzeoelektrik datchik kirish kattaligi kuch, chiqish kattaligi tok miqdori bo'lgan generator tipidagi datchiklarga kiradi. Pyzeoelektrik datchikning ishlash prinsipi pyzeoeffekt hodisasiga asoslangan, uning mohiyati shuki siqish va cho'zilish jarayonida ba'zi kristallarning qirralarida elektr zaryadlari hosil bo'ladi.

Pyzeoelektrik manometrlarning ishlash prinsipi ba'zi kristall moddalarning mexanik kuch ta'sirida elektr zaryad hosil qilish qobiliyatiga asoslangan. hodisa pyzeoeffekt deb

1 – rasm. Pyzeoelektrik manometer sxmasi

ataladi. Pezoeffekt kvars, turmalin, segnet tuzi, bariy titanat va boshqa moddalar kristallarida kuzatiladi. Bu turdagi asboblarda ko‘pincha kvars shlatiladi. Kvarsning pezoelektr effekti +500°S gacha bo‘lgan haroratga bog‘liq emas, lekin +570°S dan oshgan haroratda bu effekt nolga teng bo‘lib qoladi.

F kuch ta’sirida kristall plastinka yuzalarida paydo bo‘ladigan elektr zaryad ushbu tenglama bilan topiladi:

$$Q=K_p \cdot F \quad (1.1)$$

bu erda, K_p —pezoelektrik doimiy, Kl/N. K_p ning qiymati plastinaning o‘lchamiga bog‘liq emas va kristallning tabiati bilan belgilanadi. Kvars uchun

$$K_p=2,1 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ Kl/n.}$$

1-rasmda pezoelektrik manometrning sxemasi ko‘rsatilgan.

O‘lchanayotgan bosimni 4 membrana kuchga aylantiradi, bu kuch esa diametri 5 mm va qalinligi 1 mm bo‘lgan kvars plastinalar 2 ning ustunlarini siqilishga majbur qiladi. Vujudga kelayotgan Q elektr zaryad 1 chiqishlar orqali katta kirish qarshiligiga (10^{13} Om) ega bo‘lgan elektron kuchaytirgich 5 ga uzatiladi.

Zaryadning qiymati o‘lchanayotgan R bosim bilan quyidagicha bog‘langan:

$$Q=K_p \cdot S \cdot P \quad (1.2)$$

bu erda, S — membrananing samarali yuzi.

Asbobning inersionalligini kamaytirish uchun kamera 3 ning hajmi minimallashtiriladi.

100 mPa (1000 kgk/sm^2) gacha bosimlarni o‘lchashga imkon beruvchi pezokvarsli manometrlar tez o‘zgaruvchi bosimlarni o‘lchashda keng qo‘llanadi. Pezoeffektning afzalligi uning inersionsizligidir. Bu asboblarda bosimlari tez o‘zgaradigan jarayonlarni (kavitatsiya, portlash) o‘rganishda juda qulay. Pezoelektr manometrlarning aniqlik sinfi 1,5; 2,0.

Quyidagi parametrlarini topamiz.

1). Zaryad miqdori

$$q=K_0 \cdot F_x \text{ (Kl/N)} \quad (1)$$

K_0 – pyezoelektrik doimiy;

F_x – kuch.

2). Bitta plastina sig‘imi

$$C_0 = 0.89 \frac{\epsilon_r \cdot S_x}{d} = 0.89 \frac{\epsilon_r \cdot \pi \cdot D^2}{4 \cdot d} = 0.89 \frac{\epsilon_r \cdot \pi a b}{4 \cdot d} \text{ (pF)} \quad (2)$$

C_0 - bitta plastina sig‘imi ;

ϵ_r - dielektrik o‘tkazuvchanlik ;

D – plastina diametri;

a va b – plastina tomonlari(to‘g‘ri to‘rtburchak);

d – plastina qalinligi.

3) Qatlamlar orasidagi kuchlanish

$$U = \frac{10^{12} * n * q}{C_k + n * C_0} = \frac{q * 10^{12}}{C_k / n + C_0} \quad (\text{V}) \quad (3)$$

C_k - o'lchanayotgan zanjir sig'imi

n – plastinalar soni;

4). Datchik sezgirligi

$$S_d = \frac{U}{F_x} \quad (\text{V/N}) \quad (4)$$

S_d – datchik sezgirligi

Masalani yechish:

Berilganlar:

Material – kvars, $\epsilon_r = 4.5 * 10^{-11}$, $K_0 = 2.5 * 10^{-12}$ Kl/N; n=1; d=1mm=10⁻³m;

D=1sm=10⁻²m;

$F_x = 15$ N; $C_k = 17$ pF.

Yechish:

1) $q = K_0 * F_x = 2.5 * 10^{-12} * 15 = 37.5 * 10^{-12}$ (Kl)

2) $C_0 = 0.89 \frac{4.5 * 10^{-11} * 3.14 * 10^{-4}}{4 * 10^3} = 3.1$ (pF)

3) $U = \frac{37.5 * 10^{-12} * 10^{12}}{17/1 + 3.1} = 1.9$ (V)

4) $S_d = \frac{1.9}{15} = 0.12$ (V/N).

ADABIYOTLAR

1. O.N. Norboyev, S.M. Jovliyev. (2023). Donni maydalash texnologik jarayonini avtomatlashtirish tavsifi va tahlili // Innovations in Technology and Science Education, 2023/3/1, 2-7, 615-626
2. O.N. Norboyev, S.M. Jovliyev. (2023). Donni maydalash texnologik jarayonini avtomatlashtirish tavsifi va tahlili // Innovations in Technology and Science Education, 2023/3/1, 2-7, 615-626
3. Jovliyev, S. M. o'g'li. (2023). O'LCHASH O'ZGARTKICHLARI VA ULARNI ASBOBLARNING O'LCHASH CHEGARASI (DIAPAZONI)NI KENGAYTIRISHDA ISHLATILISHI // Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(5), 695–700

4. O.N. Norboyev, S.M. Jovliyev. (2023). MATLAB DASTURINIG SIMULINK PAKITIDAN FOYDALANIB KONTUR TOKINI IMITATION MODELLASHTIRISH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH // Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(5), 870-881
5. Jovliyev Sarvar Mustafo o'g'li. O'LCHASH NATIJALARINI QAYTA ISHLASH // Educational Research in Universal Sciences. November 2023, Volume 2, Issue 11, page 264-269
6. Jovliyev Sarvar Mustafo o'g'li. Turli tizimdagi o'lchash asboblarni tekshirish va xatoliklarini aniqlash // Educational Research in Universal Sciences. November 2023, Volume 2, Issue 11, page 283–290
7. Jovliyev Sarvar Mustafo o'g'li. (2022). MAHSULOT SIFATINI BOSHQARISH VA TAXLIL QILISH STATISTIK USULLARINING YETTI INSTRUMENT USULLARI // EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 2(6), 41–45
8. Jovliyev Sarvar Mustafo o'g'li. (2022). TEXNIKA OLIY O'QUV YURTLARI TA'LIMIDA KEYS TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH // EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 2(5), 791–794
9. Zhovliev S.M. Specialty of technological processes and production automation – profession of the XXI century // ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. –2021, May. –T.2. №.05. –C. 15-19
10. Mallayev A.R., Sharipov G.Q., Sodikov A.R., Zhovliev S.M. Mathematical modeling of dynamics formation of hydrates at pipeline natural gas transport // International Journal For Innovative Engineering and Management Research. – 2021, April. –T.10. №.4. –C. 31-35
11. Raximov A.X., Jovliyev S.M. Xolbutayeva X.E. Radio monitoring and recognition of radio emissions radio electronic equipment // International Journal For Innovative Engineering and Management Research. –2021, April. – T.10. №.4. –C. 506-507